

European Union Projects – and the Thrill of Being Part of One Coordinated by Prof. Nina Thornhill

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Abstract: Prof. Nina Thornhill has led numerous European Projects and I have had the pleasure of being part of two of them: ITN Energy SmartOPS and ITN PRONTO. This short note will reflect on these in the light of what I have experienced, enjoyed and especially learned from Prof. Thornhill. A reader who expects me to evaluate any of her technical achievements will be highly disappointed, as I am truly not an expert in her area but more kind of a novice who had the pleasure of hearing her talk about her work, in person as well as through the students that she supervised during the EU project.

Keywords: Nina, EU, Coordination, Meetings, Respect, Collaboration, Reliability, Traveling, Fun.

1. INTRODUCTION

As I have worked at ABB since 2001, many people reading this knows that I have focused on quite different research topics than Nina. Nevertheless, she has made it possible to find some common denominators to join our strengths and work towards a larger goal where the experiences and skill can come together in a very rewarding way – train new students along their road towards a PhD. As a result, she would today understand my work much better than I can understand hers... as she has closely monitored the work of students working under my partial supervision, whereas I have mostly been too occupied to try to get deeper into other students challenges.

First the time I got aware of Nina was when Dr. Alexander Horch was working on a project jointly with UCL and we were part of the same research team in Ladenburg. Alexander was always extremely positive about this wonderful professor who really has an excellent attitude towards industrially relevant challenges, is a very open and collaborative person, and on top of had an extremely smart student that even was German. Alexander said that we must be able to hire her! One or two years later Dr. Margret Bauer freshly graduated joined our research team in Ladenburg and became my office-mate. We shared the office for quite a few years and I also got to see the positive energy of Nina through Margret's personality. She was praising her supervisor, whom I unfortunately never had the pleasure to meet.

2. PROJECT COLLABORATION

Doing good creates a reputation and people also like to share good news. I had heard many things about Nina well before we met and our joint work really started with the preparation of an EU-proposal that later was granted and became ITN Energy SmartOPS. From the very start of the EU-proposal preparation (something I had never done in my life), I felt that I was in good hands. Nina and her team could guide me through such that I managed to co-author a work package that

in the project resulted in working with three students in Ladenburg. I was co-supervising Dr. Hubert Hadera and later Mr. Matteo Biondi and Mr. Robin Cartoux, all who contributed well to the project and allowed me to point the direction to talented people and help me to satisfy my curiosity about much deeper combine the area of planning and scheduling, with energy and maintenance optimization. One of the highlights of the SmartOPS project was of course the 15 talented students and the network meetings that brought us together – several times in London, Cranfield, Krakow, Bergen and Ladenburg (yes, I missed the meeting in Terni). I could also participate and present in a special session at the ESCAPE conference in Budapest.

Fig. 1. ITN SmartOPS team

One of the biggest challenges of leading a European Project is that most of the participants do not really have experience of executing such a project, neither truly the interest or time to get too deeply engaged in all the small (and bigger) bureaucratic issues that just must be fulfilled as a part of the contract. Here, the true strength of Nina very early became prominent: Her way of advising, motivating but also challenging people to just make their best efforts to carry part of this work. She made everything sound clear and logical,

explained the reasons, always was very open to ideas on how to fulfil the tasks and without ever being pushy we just got everything done. Thank you, Nina, for always being so kind and supportive! I do not even dare to think what Nina's team all did in the background (Christina and Angela), but assume that without them we would have been in big trouble...

After altogether four interesting years we were happily concluding the ITN SmartOPS project and heading towards a new one. I was fully motivated to continue working along these lines and participated in two other EU-project proposals: one related to electricity grids (not granted) and the other one actually became the follow-up project ITN EID PRONTO.

Fig. 2. Dinner celebration at ITN PRONTO meeting (Bergen)

The second project was maybe even more challenging since in the EID format the industrial partners are much more involved. So, I became the co-supervisor of Giancarlo Dalle Ave and also of Frederik Schulze-Spüntrup at NTNU. Apart from that, we also through Giancarlo had several collaborations with BASF (Ouyang) and AST-Terni (Jesus) and had I not had such an active and open student this would have been impossible. Once again, we could enter the very pleasant EU-Journey with Nina as the coordinator and she truly made at least as fantastic job also this time. We managed to bring together various elements of different research fields and really created cross-collaborations between the students. This can be heavily credited to Nina who had the vision and could gently steer us towards digging deeper together and see what comes out. Again, one of the greatest highlights were again the time we could spend together as a project team in London, Krakow, Ladenburg, Cologne, Valladolid, Terni and Trondheim. This time I could also participate in two PRONTO sessions at the IFAC DYCOPS conference in Florianópolis and at the ESCAPE conference in Eindhoven.

3. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

To summarize: from the scientific point of view these collaboration projects have been excellent and we have truly not only pushed the theoretical boundaries but also got many novel ideas tested in an industrial environment. I have had the chance to get exposed to many problems I barely knew that existed and at least gained respect of the complexity of many for me totally new research themes. The work has resulted in

numerous conference and journal papers, many of which are currently still in a peer-review phase.

Fig. 3. Nina at a ITN PRONTO dinner in Krakow

From the team point of view, Nina has an incredible talent of getting people to work together in a very positive way including every single team member. She has created a team spirit that I am especially happy about. This part of Nina is unique, and I have learned much from her. Her humbleness, and the way of always highlighting the work of her collaborators makes her even bigger. I look very much up to Nina as a leader of people who voluntary work towards a common goal with a smile in their face.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thank you, Nina, for all the good you have done to me and so many more. I hope that I can carry forward some of the positiveness that I have learned from you. I know that many of your students and EU-Project team members will do this. There will be a big gap after you step out from the university world. I wish you all the best and hope that you can now pursue all your personal goals that was not possible as you were so busy on helping many other people to reach their own ones. Thank you, Nina!!!

REFERENCES

Everyone who had the pleasure to work with Nina